

Hands On Group Activity

Instructions:

- Look at the page titled “**Field Data**”
- Use the **Darwin Core definition sheet** to help you map columns in the Field Data to columns in
 - Event
 - Occurrence
 - extendedMeasurementOrFact
- Try to **create unique identifiers** for
 - species occurrence (occurrenceID)
 - sampling events (eventID)

e.g. ID structure

PROJECT_Date_Site_Station_Sample_SPECIES

Other Reminders & notes:

- decimalLatitude + decimalLongitude should hold **midpoint** of polygons or line transects
- footprintWKT is used for **polygons, points, & line transects**
- **ALL measurements** can be placed in the extendedMeasurementOrFact
- Some info in the occurrence can be **repeated** in the eMoF e.g. organism counts, lifestage, etc.

Field Data (fictional)

Site Biscoff Bay	Date 2011-02-12	
Station G1	Station Surface temp (°C) 20.1	Transect length (m) 30 m

Transect	Quadrat	Lat start	Lon start	Lat end	Lon end	Mid-point lon	Mid-point lat	Depth min	Depth max	Zostera % cover	Aurelia aurita	Clupea harengus (adult)	Clupea harengus (juvenile)
1	1	54.501	18.559	54.501	18.572	18.5662	54.5005	0.8	4	30			
1	2	54.501	18.559	54.501	18.572	18.5662	54.5005	0.8	4	60			
1	3	54.501	18.559	54.501	18.572	18.5662	54.5005	0.8	4	85			
1		54.501	18.559	54.501	18.572	18.5662	54.5005	0.8	4		10	23	3
2		54.4856	18.5696	54.4859	18.5835	18.5766	54.4857	0.5	6		3	14	9

Event - ANSWER

<u>eventID</u>	<u>eventDate</u>	<u>locality</u>	<u>eventType</u>	<u>decimal Longitude</u>	<u>decimal Latitude</u>	<u>minimum DepthInMetres</u>	<u>maximum DepthInMetres</u>	<u>footprintWKT</u>
BB_2011-02-12-G1	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Site visit	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Transect	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	LINESTRING(18.559 54.501, 18.572 54.501)
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T02	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Transect	18.5766	54.4857	6	0.5	LINESTRING(18.5696 54.4856, 18.5835 54.4859)
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q1	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Sample	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	LINESTRING(18.559 54.501, 18.572 54.501)
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q2	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Sample	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	LINESTRING(18.559 54.501, 18.572 54.501)
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q3	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Sample	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	LINESTRING(18.559 54.501, 18.572 54.501)

Occurrence - ANSWER

<u>eventID</u>	<u>occurrenceID</u>	<u>scientificName</u>	<u>occurrenceStatus</u>	<u>basisOfRecord</u>	<u>organism Quantity</u>	<u>organism QuantityType</u>	<u>lifestage</u>
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q1	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q1_Zost	Zostera	present	<u>HumanObservation</u>	30	Percent cover	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q2	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q2_Zost	Zostera	present	<u>HumanObservation</u>	60	Percent cover	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q3	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q3_Zost	Zostera	present	<u>HumanObservation</u>	85	Percent cover	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Aaurita	Aurelia aurita	present	<u>HumanObservation</u>	10	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Aaurita	Aurelia aurita	present	<u>HumanObservation</u>	3	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-adult	Clupea <u>harengus</u>	present	<u>HumanObservation</u>	23	Individuals	adult
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-adult	Clupea <u>harengus</u>	present	<u>HumanObservation</u>	14	Individuals	Adult
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-juv	Clupea <u>harengus</u>	present	<u>HumanObservation</u>	3	Individuals	Juvenile
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-juv	Clupea <u>harengus</u>	present	<u>HumanObservation</u>	9	Individuals	juvenile

<u>eventID</u>	<u>occurrenceID</u>	<u>measurement Type</u>	<u>measurement Value</u>	<u>measurement Unit</u>
BB_2011-02-12-G1		Surface water temp	20.1	Degrees <u>celsius</u>
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1		Transect length	30	metres
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1		Transect length	30	metres
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1_Q1	BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q1_Zost	% cover	30	percent
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1_Q2	BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q2_Zost	% cover	60	Percent
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1_Q3	BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q3_Zost	% cover	85	percent
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-adult	Life stage	<u>adult</u>	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-adult	Life stage	<u>adult</u>	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-juv	Life stage	<u>juvenile</u>	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-juv	Life stage	<u>juvenile</u>	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Aaurita	10	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Aaurita	3	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-adult	23	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-adult	14	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-juv	3	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-juv	9	Individuals	